

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES IN TEACHING INFORMATICS

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Abstract

The article examines the advantages of preparing various lectures for teaching computer science in the Visual Basic programming environment, as well as preparing multimedia tools with the help of this environment in practical exercises.

Keywords: Visual Basic, education, multimedia, programming, informatics

Multimedia technologies are a group of technologies based on the use of computer visualization technology, including integrated images, solving didactic problems. They have the following functions: integrativeness, interconnectedness of subjects of education, automation, multifacetedness and generalization. The main application of interactive multimedia for learning is in a learning situation where the learner is given control so that he can view the material in his own space and according to his individual interests, needs and cognitive processes [2]. Educational technology is the study and ethical practice of facilitating learning and enhancing achievement through the creation, use and management of appropriate technological processes and resources [1, p. 169-171].

In the system of methodical training of informatics teachers in pedagogical universities, one of its components should be the training of a new type of teacher - a specialist in the pedagogical and organizational application of information technologies. On the other hand, training in the technology of developing multimedia educational programs requires their creators to have knowledge both in the field of the technology of writing the programs themselves, and in the field of developing an educational program for the educational program taking into account the possibilities of programming tools and application development tools.

The distinctive features of the modern concept of teaching informatics in educational institutions of Azerbaijan are: recognition of the high development potential of informatics and giving it the status of a fundamental subject; an idea about the structure of the field of informatics according to modern views; a modular description of the studied subject area, unlike the previously used discipline; using modern technologies for the systematic modular formation of the training content, which allows to form a program that takes into account the features of the learner's future professional activity based on the activity approach and on the basis of state educational standards; his personal interests and characteristics.

Understanding the goals of teaching informatics at school in connection with the deepening of ideas about the general education and worldview potential of this subject shows the need to distinguish several stages in

learning the basics of informatics and forming information culture in the school learning process.

The main goals of the informatics course in high school are to acquire computer literacy and form the basics of information culture. This leads to a two-level system, where the content of teaching informatics in high school should be differentiated according to interests and should be aimed at pre-professional training of students. According to the new approach, the third stage (grades 10-11) should have the character of specialized education differentiated by its scope and content, depending on the interests and orientation of professional training of schoolchildren. In particular, here it is possible to study programming languages and methods of computational mathematics in depth, to work with ready-made software for solving practical problems from various areas of a person's professional activity: modeling, experimental data processing, multimedia technologies, computer networks, publishing systems, working with graphics.

Considering that one of the main tasks of the differentiation of the content of education at school is pre-professional training in the chosen field of specialization of the student, as well as preparation for continuous education in this field, it can be considered that informatics and information technologies are one of the mandatory components of the content of specialized education in any field of specialization of the school. must be converted.

Ramin Mahmudzadeh, Ismayil Sadigov, Naida Isayeva offer six educational units for in-depth study of informatics in high school in the program of continuous 8th grade informatics subject for secondary school [3, p. 4]:

1. Information;
2. Multimedia;
3. Programming;
4. Computer;
5. Applied programs;
6. Information society and the Internet.

In the 9th grade informatics program, they offer five teaching units for in-depth study of informatics in high school [4, p. 4]:

1. Coding;
2. Computer;
3. Applied programs;
4. Programming;
5. Information technologies.

Among the educational units listed above, in our opinion, taking into account the development of computer technology, the most interesting are "Programming", "Multimedia" and "Application programs".

When studying programming, the question arises about the content of a high school computer science course - what programming languages should be studied, whether it is worth introducing students (future computer science teachers) to the latest technologies in the field of software development, or whether it is enough to consider that the learning objectives of programming such as Basic and Pascal to teach classical principles of structured programming using examples of educational languages and older versions of professional languages?

In order to learn programming in the Python programming language, future computer science teachers must master other programming languages and be able to design programs. Experiments show that the Pascal programming language taught in the first semester of the 4th year of Nakhchivan State University helps them master the Python language in the second semester. Therefore, a future computer science teacher should be able to program comfortably in each of these programming languages. Also, he should master programming in the Visual Basic environment, which is object-oriented programming, so that in the future he can create macros in the Visual Basic for Application environment included in the application programs and simplify the work mechanism. It should be noted that in the TIOBE index (the TIOBE programming community index - an index that evaluates the popularity of programming languages based on the calculation of the results of search queries containing the name of the language), Python ranks 1st and Visual

Basic 6th in the ranking of programming languages for May 2024 (picture 1.) [5]. We think that parallel programming also has a superior role in language acquisition.

We also present the statements of N. Virt, the author of the Pascal programming language: "The development of the Pascal language had two main goals. First, to create a language that allows programming to be taught as a systematic discipline. It should be reflected in this language in a simple and natural way. Second, to develop versions of this language that are both reliable and efficient for modern computers...". Currently, PascalABC.NET is the most widely used environment. Therefore, in our opinion, systematic programming training should be conducted on the basis of the Pascal language, and then transition to the study of general programming technology using object-oriented approach and visual programming technologies. For example, Visual Basic, Visual C, Delphi. Studying these languages together with other mediums allows you to switch to the study of another profile course called "Multimedia".

In the 8th-9th grade of the informatics subject in the school, the topics and content of it should be carried out within the framework of specialized courses determined by the social order of the society on the one hand, and on the other hand by the current state of information technologies. Taking into account these requirements, we believe that the most important when choosing specialized courses are courses to learn programming languages and the basics of multimedia technology. In preparation for this, the right choice of programming language plays a key role in pedagogical specializations in informatics.

TIOBE Index for May 2024

May Headline: Fortran in the top 10, what is going on?

I have received a lot of questions why Fortran entered the top 10 again after more than 20 years. The TIOBE index just publishes what has been measured. There are for instance more than 1,000 hits for "Fortran programming" on Amazon, which is the leading company in books. New cool languages such as Kotlin and Rust, barely hit 300 books for the same search query. So, what is going on? First of all, the Fortran language is still evolving since its inception in 1957. Less than half a year ago, the new ISO Fortran 2023 definition was published.

The main reason for Fortran's resurrection is the growing importance of numerical/mathematical computing. Despite lots of competitors in this field, Fortran has its reason for existence. Let's briefly check the competition out. Python: choice number one, but slow, MATLAB: very easy to use for mathematical computation but it comes with expensive licenses, C/C++: mainstream and fast, but they have no native mathematical computation support, R: very similar to Python, but less popular and slow, Julia: the rising new kid on the block, but not mature yet. And in this jungle of languages, Fortran appears to be fast, having native mathematical computation support, mature, and free of charge. Silently, slowly but surely, Fortran gains ground. It is surprising but undeniable. --Paul Jansen CEO TIOBE Software

The TIOBE Programming Community index is an indicator of the popularity of programming languages. The index is updated once a month. The ratings are based on the number of skilled engineers world-wide, courses and third party vendors. Popular web sites Google, Amazon, Wikipedia, Bing and more than 20 others are used to calculate the ratings. It is important to note that the TIOBE index is not about the *best* programming language or the language in which *most lines of code* have been written.

The index can be used to check whether your programming skills are still up to date or to make a strategic decision about what programming language should be adopted when starting to build a new software system. The definition of the TIOBE index can be found [here](#).

May 2024	May 2023	Change	Programming Language	Ratings	Change
1	1		Python	16.33%	+2.88%
2	2		C	9.98%	-3.37%
3	4	▲	C++	9.53%	-2.43%
4	3	▼	Java	8.69%	-3.53%
5	5		C#	6.49%	-0.94%
6	7	▲	JavaScript	3.01%	+0.57%
7	6	▼	Visual Basic	2.01%	-1.83%
8	12	▲	Go	1.60%	+0.61%

Picture 1. TOIBE index

Among RAD - systems, the Microsoft Visual Basic environment is specially selected. This environment has capabilities ranging from simple one-window add-ons to creating database management applications. Microsoft Visual Basic uses Visual Basic as the programming language. The new capabilities of the Visual Basic programming language further strengthen its position. The Microsoft Visual Basic environment is suitable for developing practically any type of add-in. With the help of this language, it is possible to create very powerful autonomous applications, games and service utilities in less time than in other programming languages. ActiveX technology allows you to write add-ons with the support of the Internet, the possibilities of which can be limited only by your imagination.

Thus, in the article, the Visual Basic visual programming language can be used to create any educational computer programs.

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